

A NOVEL APPROACH TO MODELLING OF FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITES WITH CARBON NANOTUBES

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1. Introduction

Fiber-reinforced polymer composites possess excellent stiffness and strength, however their toughness is limited by early damage initiation. In cross-ply and woven laminates loaded in tension the damage starts at strains that are 4-5 times lower than the failure strain of the composites. This damage appears in the form of matrix cracks in transverse plies.

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have been shown to influence the initiation and development of damage in fiber-reinforced composites. Combined analysis of acoustic emission measurements and X-ray/SEM observations in [1, 2] confirmed that CNTs, dispersed in the matrix, have a hindering effect on the formation of transverse cracks. This may be attributed to toughening of the matrix, strengthening of the fiber/matrix interface or to redistribution of stress concentrations between fibers in the presence of CNTs.

In order to better understand the effect of CNTs on the stress distribution in unidirectional composites, we propose a novel Finite Element (FE) model that combines microscale fibers and nanoscale reinforcements in a single simulation without any intermediate homogenization of properties and transfer of parameters from one scale to another.

2. FE modeling

2.1 State-of-the-art

The main difficulty in the development of a FE model where fibers and nanotubes are considered simultaneously is to deal with a very large difference of their sizes. For instance, diameters of CNTs and carbon fibers differ more than 350 times. There exist models in the literature that predict the effect of CNTs on mechanical properties of polymers in the absence of fibers. Most of these models are based on the direct implementation of CNT geometry into the matrix [3-8]. Such an approach assures that the matrix mesh continuously passes to the CNT mesh with junctions in mutual

nodes. The mesh around tips of the CNTs becomes, however, very fine due to CNTs' high aspect ratios (commonly in the range of 50-200). The direct implementation of CNTs in a 3D model of a fiber-reinforced composite would lead to a very high number of elements. The second drawback of the approach is impossibility to use hexahedral or even hex-dominated meshes. The only remaining option is to use a free tetrahedral mesh, but due to constrained degrees of freedom and geometry of the element it is less favorable for modeling of CNTs.

In the open literature, three-dimensional (3D) models that simultaneously combine micro-scale and nano-scale reinforcements in a composite are virtually non-existent. Even in the 2D formulation the availability of such models is very limited. In [9] a 2D problem of wavy nanotubes distributed in the polymer matrix between glass fibers was considered. To overcome numerical difficulties mentioned above, the problem was simplified towards a less realistic ratio of the fiber diameter and the CNT diameter (less than 10 times). The direct implementation of tens of thousands of CNTs in a model with microscopic fibers is, thus, not the most suitable approach.

Ideally, the technique for FE modeling of CNTs in a composite should overcome the following difficulties:

- The number of elements overall in the model should not increase significantly after the CNT introduction. In other words, it should not lead to the refinement of the matrix mesh to accommodate CNT tips.
- The type of elements to be used should remain hexahedral since tetrahedral elements have significantly lower computational accuracy. Moreover, a larger number of these elements is required to fill the matrix volume.

The Embedded Regions (ER) technique, implemented in Abaqus(TM) software, satisfies these conditions with good accuracy and calculation efficiency.

2.2 The ER technique

The ER technique is a promising technique for implementation of CNTs in a FE model of a composite. It combines two independent FE meshes in a single model. Based on the principle of equal displacements of respective nodes, this method works as follows.

Fig.1 shows the case when a 1D beam element (element 1: embedded element) lies in a 3D solid element (element 2: host element). Element 1 is formed by nodes A and B, element 2 is formed by nodes a, b, c, d, e, f, g, and h. If the host element set includes element 2 and the embedded element set contains element 1 Abaqus will attempt to find out if any embedded nodes (A and B) lie within host element 2. If node A is found to lie close to the a-b-f-e face of element 2, all degrees of freedom at node A are constrained to nodes a, b, f, and e, with appropriate weight factors. The latter are determined based on the geometric location of node A in element 2. Similarly, if node B is found to lie inside element 2 - all degrees of freedom at node B are constrained to nodes a, b, c, d, e, f, g, and h with appropriate weight factors. The latter are determined based on the geometric location of node B in element 2.

Fig.1. The principle of the RE technique.

ER technique has several significant advantages in comparison with the direct implementation approach. The matrix mesh is independent of the mesh of the embedded objects. Hence, hexahedral elements can be used and no extra elements to operate with CNTs geometry features are required. There are, however, limitations. The ones that are relevant for the present study are listed below:

- Host elements cannot be embedded themselves.
- The distance of embedded nodes from the host region is controlled by a fractional exterior tolerance value.
- The material defined for the host element is not replaced by the material defined for the embedded element at the same location of the integration point.

- Additional respective mass and stiffness (of CNTs) due to the embedded elements are added to the model.

In order to understand whether the ER technique is suitable for FE modeling of CNTs in the matrix, it was validated on the example of a single CNT. Once successful, it can be applied to a full-scale model with thousands of CNTs in between microscopic fibers.

The problem of a finite cylindrical reinforcement (CNT) under unidirectional tension was taken as a case study. This problem is also known as the Cox problem [10]. Three different ways for modeling of a CNT were considered:

- Direct geometry implementation: a CNT is modeled as a cylinder. A single mesh is used in the model. It is based on 3D solid elements (C3D8) that have 8 nodes.
- Embedded Region technique: a CNT is modeled as a “wire”. Two separate meshes are used: one for the matrix and one for the CNT. The CNT mesh is based on 1D beam elements (B31) that have 2 nodes and the matrix mesh is based on 3D solid elements (C3D8) that have 8 nodes.
- Embedded Region technique: the CNT is modeled as a cylinder. Two separate meshes are used: one for the matrix and one for the CNT. Both meshes are based on 3D solid elements (C3D8) which have 8 nodes.

For validation the longitudinal stress (σ_x) along the fiber central axis, the shear stress (σ_{xy}) in the matrix close to the fiber surface and the homogenized longitudinal stiffness are calculated. Average stresses for the homogenization were calculated via reaction forces on the model boundaries.

The ER technique showed good correlation with the direct geometry implementation as well as with the analytical solution of the COX problem. It was concluded that under the assumption of the perfect contact between the matrix and the CNT the ER technique can be used for modeling of CNTs.

2.3 A hybrid model of a composite with CNTs

In order to create a FE model of a UD composite reinforced with CNTs an adequate geometrical description of CNTs' placement in the representative volume element (RVE) is needed. The task is twofold: first, to model individual CNTs that are naturally curved and, second, to control their orientation and placement between the fibers.

As discussed earlier the direct CNT geometry implementation requires quite complex work with the matrix mesh, therefore, most of the available models are based on quite severe simplifications. For example, CNTs are often assumed to be straight [3-7, 11, 12], and their distribution is often simplified to a regular unidirectional packing. Such assumptions introduce additional errors in the FE predictions. In reality carbon nanotubes are randomly curved in a 3D space [13] and the waviness has a significant effect on properties of the polymer and composite [8].

An algorithm for generation of randomly oriented and distributed CNTs that are naturally curved was developed and performed in Matlab. Four different strategies for CNTs placement between fibers were considered (Fig.2): CNTs randomly dispersed in the matrix, CNTs clustered in agglomerates and CNTs grown on fiber surfaces (either randomly oriented or radially aligned). Respectively, four different generation algorithms were developed. For simplicity the model of two fiber quarters was considered with a fiber volume fraction of 60%. This geometrical description of the RVE is further used to investigate the effect of CNTs on the stress distribution in the composite.

2.3.1 FE model

A fully parametrical 3D FE model of a UD composite reinforced with CNTs under transversal tension was developed using Python programming. The RVE size was $5.66\mu\text{m} \times 5.66\mu\text{m} \times 2.83\mu\text{m}$. To the right side of the RVE a strain of 0.15% is applied (Fig.3). On the other 5 RVE sides the symmetry boundary conditions are applied. This simulates a model problem of hexagonally packed fibers under transversal tension. Due to the symmetry the total applied transverse strain is 0.3%.

The ER technique described and validated above is applied to solve this 3D problem. CNTs are modeled as curved cylinders with a circular cross-section, a radius $R_{CNT} = 9 \text{ nm}$ and a length of $0.7 \mu\text{m}$. The volume fraction of CNTs in the matrix was fixed to 0.17%. This value corresponds to 0.25% in the weight fraction of CNTs in the matrix. In the case of agglomerated CNTs the volume fraction of CNTs inside the two agglomerates is equal to 0.91%.

For simplicity CNTs were assumed to be isotropic with the Poisson's ratio $\nu=0.4$ and the Young's modulus of 475.3 GPa. CNTs were introduced one by one and meshed with 3D solid elements (C3D8).

Fig.2. CNTs placement strategies: (a) dispersed in the matrix, (b) clustered in agglomerates, (c) and (d) grown on fibers surface (without and with preferential orientation).

The matrix and carbon fibers were modeled as solid bodies and meshed with the same type of elements. The elastic properties of the matrix were Young's modulus $E_m=3$ GPa and Poisson's ratio $\nu=0.4$. After solving the FE problem the post-processing procedure is applied.

Fig.3. Schematics of the applied boundary conditions.

2.3.2 Through- thickness stress field analysis

The stress field analysis is performed as follows. First, the FE model is created: the geometry, FE mesh and boundary conditions. Then, as a result of the FE analysis the stress fields are obtained: stresses are calculated in the integration points of every element of the matrix and gathered in created output *.dat* files. These *.dat* files are used as an input for the Matlab routine, which is written for post-processing of stress fields into the stress distribution histograms.

Fig.4. Two areas of interest for stress field analysis: (a) the matrix and (b) the fiber/matrix interface.

Stresses are analyzed in two areas of interest: in the matrix and at the fiber/matrix interface rings - matrix elements closest to the fiber surface. In the matrix, two stresses are considered: the maximal principal stress and von Mises stress. At the fiber/matrix interface, the normal stress (σ_r) and shear stress ($\sigma_{r\phi}$), with respect to local cylindrical coordinate systems placed at the fiber centers, are calculated (Fig. 4b).

In order to quantitatively compare the obtained stress fields, the probability of finding a certain stress value in a given area of interest is investigated. The procedure is schematically illustrated on Figure 5. In the thickness direction the 3D stress fields are divided into the stress fields in a sequence of layers.

There are 27 layers in total in the model. Stresses belonging to the different layers are stored and processed separately.

For each layer a histogram curve is created to determine "frequency" of the appearance of a certain stress value in a given area of interest. It is calculated as a volume of elements with the found stress values divided by the total volume of elements in the given area of interest, either for the matrix or the fiber/matrix interface rings.

Once histograms are created for each layer, a 3D plot is constructed (Fig.5c): the abscissa is the stress range divided on intervals with increment R , the ordinate is the sequence of through-thickness layers of elements and the color means the probability of finding a certain interval of stress: the red color indicates a higher frequency of appearing such a stress in the area of interest.

Then curves for the maximum and dominant curves are created. The principle of their creation is as follows. As shown in Fig.7 the maximum stress curve consists of the highest values of stresses in the histogram – one stress value per layer. This curve is then transformed into a 2D plot where the abscissa is the sequence of through-thickness layers of elements and the ordinate is a maximum stress value appeared in the layer. The maximum stress curve built from the maximal principal stress histogram within the matrix area is shown in Fig.7a. From such plots the existence of high stresses can be compared. However, neither their intensity (the occupied volume) nor their position in the XY plane can be investigated from these plots alone.

The same principle is used to create curves of the dominant stress. The difference is that stresses that are analyzed are not the highest in the layer but dominant. The dominance is determined by the volume of elements which have stresses within a certain stress interval (the most red in the histogram). The dominant curve obtained from the maximal principal stress histogram within the matrix area is shown in Fig.7b.

Then the *.dat* files with maximum as well as with dominant curves data are created as an output.

Fig.5. The stress field analysis: (a) obtaining of stress fields, (b) dividing the stress fields by element layers and (c) creating histogram curves.

Fig.7. Creation of the maximum stress curve (a) and the dominant stress curve (b) from the stress distribution histogram

2.4 Results and discussion

The goal of the study is to investigate the influence of CNTs on the stress distribution in a UD composite with particular focus on different CNT positions..

Four placement strategies for CNTs were considered: CNTs uniformly distributed in polymer matrix, CNTs clustered in agglomerates, CNTs grown on fiber surfaces – randomly oriented and aligned (Fig.2). Geometrical characteristics (diameter and length) and material properties of CNTs were assumed to be the same in all the cases (Section 2.3.1).

Curves for the maximum and dominant stresses are shown in Fig.8. The black curves refer to the pure matrix case without CNTs are added as a reference. These stresses for the case of agglomerates are quite different in comparison with the other cases. Sharp stress peaks are located in the middle of the RVE agglomerates are located. Depending on a stress component, the difference with the other strategies varies from 25 to 150%. The most sensible stress is maximal principal stress.

For other strategies the difference appears to be less pronounced. Curves for materials with CNTs have a tendency to lie above the reference curve, which means that the highest stresses in nano-engineered composite are higher than those in a composite without CNTs. These extreme stresses are very few and very local. At the same time, the dominant curves of the maximal principal stress for CNT reinforced composites are mainly lower than for the reference one.

In order to investigate the average shift of stresses due to the introduction of CNTs, the maximum and dominant stresses were averaged through the thickness. The case of CNT agglomerates was not considered for this averaging due to much higher peak stresses.

For all strategies of CNT incorporation in the composite, the average maximum value of the maximal principal stress increases. CNTs grown on fiber surfaces and randomly oriented generate the highest stress and its average dominant stress is just a bit lower than the highest stress. The case of uniformly dispersed CNTs in the matrix appears to generate the lowest dominant stress. The average maximal principal stress in the model is also decreased. This strategy shows the lowest increase of the average maximum von Mises stress.

Fig.8. The maximum values curves for different stresses: (a) maximal principal stress in matrix, (b) von Mises stress in matrix, (c) the normal stress at the fiber/matrix interface and (d) shear stress at the fiber/matrix interface.

CNTs grown on fibers and randomly oriented show the best results near the fiber/matrix interface: all of the average values (both the maximum and dominant for normal and shear stresses) are decreased the most. Localization of CNTs near the fiber surface without predefined orientation allows to suppress normal and shear interface stresses.

CNTs grown on fibers and aligned might be used for decreasing the dominant von Mises stress and for reducing the maximum normal stresses on fiber surfaces.

Conclusions

In the present study the ER technique was fully validated and compared with the equivalent single-mesh model (a direct geometrical implementation of a CNT cylinder into the matrix). Results from the ER technique have shown good correlation with those obtained from the single-mesh model and the Cox solution.

The influence of CNTs on stress fields in a UD composite was investigated. The main focus of such analysis was on the micro-scale stress concentrations. Our results indicate that agglomerates of CNTs create additional micro-scale stress concentrators. They increase stresses in the matrix that can eventually lead to the formation of microcracks.

The proposed approach to modeling of fiber-reinforced composites with carbon nanotubes is a promising tool to guide future developments in the field of nano-engineered composites.

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References

1. De Greef, N., et al., *The effect of carbon nanotubes on the damage development in carbon fiber/epoxy composites*. Carbon, 2011. **49**(14): p. 4650-4664.
2. Yokozeki, T., Y. Iwahori, and S. Ishiwata, *Matrix cracking behaviors in carbon fiber/epoxy laminates filled with cup-stacked carbon nanotubes (CSCNTs)*. Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2007. **38**(3): p. 917-924.
3. Li, X.T., et al., *Computational modeling and evaluation of the thermal behavior of randomly distributed single-walled carbon nanotube/polymer composites*. Computational Materials Science, 2012. **63**: p. 207-213.
4. Kirtania, S. and D. Chakraborty, *Multi-scale modeling of carbon nanotube reinforced composites with a fiber break*. Materials & Design, 2012. **35**: p. 498-504.
5. Bhuiyan, M.A., et al., *Defining the lower and upper limit of the effective modulus of CNT/polypropylene composites through integration of modeling and experiments*. Composite Structures, 2013. **95**: p. 80-87.
6. Chen, X.L. and Y.J. Liu, *Square representative volume elements for evaluating the effective material properties of carbon nanotube-based composites*. Computational Materials Science, 2004. **29**(1): p. 1-11.
7. Joshi, U.A., S.C. Sharma, and S.P. Harsha, *Effect of carbon nanotube orientation on the mechanical properties of nanocomposites*. Composites Part B-Engineering, 2012. **43**(4): p. 2063-2071.
8. Li, C.Y. and T.W. Chou, *Failure of carbon nanotube/polymer composites and the effect of nanotube waviness*. Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2009. **40**(10): p. 1580-1586.
9. Li, C.Y. and T.W. Chou, *Modeling of damage sensing in fiber composites using carbon nanotube networks*. Composites Science and Technology, 2008. **68**(15-16): p. 3373-3379.
10. van den Heuvel, P.W.J., *Failure Phenomena in Carbon/epoxy Microcomposite Model Systems*1995: Instituut Vervolgopleidingen, Eindhoven University of Technology.
11. Li, C.Y. and T.W. Chou, *Multiscale Modeling of carbon nanotube reinforced polymer composites*. Journal of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology, 2003. **3**(5): p. 423-430.
12. Rafiee, R. and R.M. Moghadam, *Simulation of impact and post-impact behavior of carbon nanotube reinforced polymer using multi-scale finite element modeling*. Computational Materials Science, 2012. **63**: p. 261-268.
13. Savvas, D.N., V. Papadopoulos, and M. Papadrakakis, *The effect of interfacial shear strength on damping behavior of carbon nanotube reinforced composites*.

International Journal of Solids and Structures, 2012. **49**(26): p. 3823-38373837.